

Francis Brett Garth

Temirboyeva Muaddat

Student, UzSWLU, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Scientific advisor: **Mukhammedova N.E** ;PhD,dots

Annotatsiya: Makur maqolada ingliz adabiyotining yetuk vakillaridan biri bo'lgan Francis Bret Gars (Francis Brett Garth) ning hayot va ijod yo'li haqida so'z yuritiladi. Uning haqiqiy ijod gulshaniga kirib kelishi uchun hissa qo'shgan va unga mashhurlik olib kelgan asarlari ,hikoya va she'rlari tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: qo'llab - quvvatlamoq, nashr etildi, qat'iy belgilanganlik, taniqli yozuvchi

Abstract: The represented article deal with the life and creative path of Francis Brett Garth, one of the mature representatives of English literature. His works, stories and poems, which contributed to his entry into the real world of creativity and brought him popularity, are analyzed.

Key words: support, publish, rigidity, well- known writer

On August 25, 1836, Francis Brett Garth was born in Albany, New York, where he also taught Greek in colleges. Frances Brett is his full name. Francis Brett Hart's father temporarily changed his last name to Hart and Hart, and his name was Brett. After his father passed away young, the future author had to support himself, and in 1854—shortly after the "gold rush" began—he came to California and tried his hand at a variety of jobs. In 1856, Bret Hart published his

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first short stories in *The Californian*, a publication he also edited. In the future, he also released *The Overland Monthly* (1868–1871), the first important magazine in America's western states. . In the 1870s, already a well-known writer, Garth lived in New York, and then - partly for material reasons, partly due to the aggravated conflict with the American public, caused by the rigidity and intransigence of the writer's civic position - he left for Europe: he was an American consul in the Prussian city of Krefeld, then in Glasgow. He spent the rest of his life in England. Died 5 May 1902 in Camberley of throat cancer.

Bret Garth owns the novel "Gabriel Conroy" (1875), a number of stories, of which the later trilogy "The Steppe Foundling", "Susie" and "Clarence" (the action takes place during the American Civil War), original poems, popular in their time literary parodies (on Dickens, Charlotte Bronte, Victor Hugo, etc.) and even a play written in collaboration with Mark Twain. However, stories brought him the greatest popularity, and in the stories - images of ordinary people of the Wild West, especially girlish and female ones. Quite early, Garth's works penetrated into Russia (the first publication was in 1872). One of his first translators was Nikolai Chernyshevsky (who was then in exile in Yakutia). In 1873, several short stories and essays by Garth about California life were published in the journal "Vestnik Evropy" in Russian. The first separate edition of "California Stories" was published in 1887. Bret Garth immediately became a favorite of the Russian public. He was read and loved by people from a wide variety of camps. He was translated and published in literary magazines; collections of his stories appeared on the book market; they were published both for intelligent readers and for the people. Already in 1895, the collected works of Bret Garth in six volumes were

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published in St. Petersburg. Albany, the state capital of New York, is where Harte was born in 1836. He was given the name Francis Brett after his great-grandfather. His father, Henry, changed the spelling of the family name from Hart to Harte when he was a little child. Bernard Hart, an Orthodox Jewish immigrant who prospered as a businessman and was one of the founding members of the New York Stock Exchange, was Henry's father. Bret's mother, Elizabeth Rebecca Ostrander Hart, grew up in a Dutch Reformed church and was of English and Dutch descent. Later, Francis opted to go by Bret Harte instead of his middle name, which he spelled with a single "t." Harte, a notable New York landowner and descendant of Francis Rombouts, was of French Huguenot and Dutch heritage. An avid reader as a boy, Harte published his first work at age 11, a satirical poem titled "Autumn Musings", now lost. Rather than attracting praise, the poem garnered ridicule from his family. As an adult, he recalled to a friend, "Such a shock was their ridicule to me that I wonder that I ever wrote another line of verse."

His formal schooling ended when he was 13, in 1849. On August 11, 1862, in San Rafael, California, Harte wed Anna Griswold. The marriage had a difficult beginning. Early Harte biographer Henry C. Merwin privately stated that she was "very impossible to live with" and that she was "hampered by acute jealousy." Harte's first short story was published in The Atlantic Monthly in October 1863 after James T. Fields, the esteemed magazine's editor, received a recommendation for Harte from the well-known pastor Thomas Starr King. Harte and Charles Henry Webb co-founded The Californian, a new literary newspaper, in 1864. He tutored poet Ina Coolbrith and became acquainted with her. Bookseller Anton Roman

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commissioned Harte to edit a collection of California poetry in 1865; it was intended to be a showcase of the best California authors. There were only 19 poets in the book *Outcroppings* when it was published, many of them Harte's acquaintances (including Ina Coolbrith and Charles Warren Stoddard). The book generated some controversy because Harte attacked California literature in the preface, blaming the "monotone atmosphere" of the state for its subpar poetry. Although the book received high recognition in the East, his comments offended many journalists and poets in the West.

In order to promote regional works, Roman Anton launched *The Overland Monthly* in 1868, and Harte was appointed editor of the publication. *The Overland Monthly* was more in tune with California's pioneering excitement.

Selected works[edit]

Bret Harte's gravestone in the churchyard of St Peter's Church, Frimley, Surrey, England

Inscription on gravestone: "Death shall reap the braver harvest."

Outcroppings (1865), editor

Condensed Novels and Other Papers (1867)

Tennessee's Partner (short story; 1869)

The Luck of Roaring Camp, and Other Sketches (1870)

"Plain Language from Truthful James", aka "The Heathen Chinee" (1870)

Poems (1871)

The Heart's Foundation (1873)

The Tales of the Argonauts (1875)

Gabriel Conroy (1876).

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Dramatic and musical adaptations:

-Several film versions of "The Outcasts of Poker Flat" have been made, including one in 1937 with Preston Foster and another in 1952 with Dale Robertson.

-Tennessee's Partner (1955) with John Payne and Ronald Reagan was based on the story of the same name.

-Paddy Chayefsky's treatment of the film version of Paint Your Wagon seems to borrow from "Tennessee's Partner": two close friends—one named "Pardner"—share the same woman. The Spaghetti Western Four of the Apocalypse is based on "The Outcasts of Poker Flat" and "The Luck of Roaring Camp".

-The Soviet movie Armed and Dangerous (Russian: Вооружён и очень опасен, 1977) is based on Gabriel Conroy and another of Harte's stories.

-Operas based on "The Outcasts of Poker Flat" include those by Samuel Adler and by Stanford Beckler.

-The actor Craig Hill was cast as Harte in the 1956 episode, "Year of Destiny", on the syndicated anthology series Death Valley Days, hosted by Stanley Andrews.

-The Year of destiny" is 1857, when Harte arrived in California. First a stagecoach guard, then a newspaper editor and schoolteacher, he slowly finds fame as a western writer.

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